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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	09/06/2022
Grant Signatory	Hans Bruyninckx	EEA	

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	08/06/2022
Work Package Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	08/06/2022
Task leader	Joana Lobo Vicente	EEA	08/06/2022

Responsible author	Joana Lobo Vicente
Short name of institution	EEA
Co-authors	Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Antje Gerofke, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 2

Table of contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	4
2	Glossary	5
3	Abstract/Summary	6
4	Introduction	7
5	Phthalates indicator	8
5.1	Information.....	8
5.2	Time patterns.....	8
5.2.1	BBzP	10
5.2.2	DEHP Σ (5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)	11
5.2.3	DEHP Σ (5oxo-MEHP +5OH-MEHP)	14
5.2.4	DEP	16
5.2.5	DiBP	17
5.2.6	DiDP	18
5.2.7	DiNP	21
5.2.8	DnBP	24
5.2.9	DINCH	25
5.3	TAB methodology	28
5.3.1	Definition.....	28
5.3.2	Disaggregation	28
5.3.3	Method of measurement	30
5.3.4	Method of estimation	30
5.4	TAB additional information	30
5.4.1	Monitoring assessment	30
5.4.2	Health impact assessment	30
5.4.3	EU-level assessment	31
5.5	TAB references.....	32
6	Pesticide indicator.....	35
6.1	Information.....	35
6.1.1	Geographical differences indicator.....	35
6.1.2	Health impact indicator	40
6.2	TAB time pattern.....	43
6.3	Interpretation	43
6.3.1	Geographical differences indicator.....	43
6.3.2	Health impact indicator	44

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 3

6.4	TAB methodology	45
6.4.1	Definition.....	45
6.4.2	Disaggregation	45
6.4.3	Method of measurement.....	45
6.4.4	Method of estimation	45
6.5	TAB additional information.....	47
6.5.1	Monitoring assessment.....	47
6.5.2	Health impact assessment.....	47
6.5.3	EU-level assessment.....	48
6.6	TAB contact.....	49
7	Conclusions	50

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 4

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Joana Lobo Vicente (EEA)

Jurgen Buekers (VITO)

Jos Bessems (VITO)

Ann Colles (VITO)

Liese Gilles (VITO)

Antje Gerofke (UBA)

Contributors

Greet Schoeters (VITO)

Catherine Ganzleben (EEA)

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 5

2 Glossary

BBzP	Benzyl butyl phthalate
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
DEHP	Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate
DEP	Diethyl phthalate
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DiDP	Di-isodecyl phthalate (all C10 phthalates including DPHP)
DINCH	1,2-Cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid diisononyl ester
DiNP	Diisononyl phthalate
DnBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate
EEA	European Environment Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	Human Biomonitoring Initiative in Europe
HBM-GV	Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values
IPCHEM	Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
SVHC	Substance of very high concern
TWI	Tolerable Weekly Intake
UBA	German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt)
VITO	Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek)
WP	Work Package

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 6

3 Abstract/Summary

This deliverable AD5.8 is a follow-up of the AD5.6, with an updated version of indicators for some metabolite phthalates as well as pesticides. The policy implications of these indicators are also discussed.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 7

4 Introduction

As per the previous deliverable AD5.6, the indicators developed will facilitate the interpretation of the newly derived HBM data and include results from the aligned studies, where possible. As singular data will be available, stratification can be done as required for optimal interpretation.

In this deliverable AD5.8, we show the indicators for pesticides together with “time pattern” indicators for phthalates. Here, data for children from DEMOCOPHES (2010-2012) are compared to those from the aligned studies (2014-2021).

In AD5.6, phthalate indicators have been derived for different geographical regions, ages and sex. Additionally, indicators have been derived for a comparison with HBM-GVs for some phthalates. The potential of these indicators is discussed.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 8

5 Phthalates indicator

5.1 Information

The rationale behind the indicators for „time patterns“ is to compare median values of phthalate metabolites for children (6-11 years) from the DEMOCOPHES survey (2010-2012) with median values from the HBM4EU aligned studies (2014-2021), **as an approximation** whether the degree of regulation has had an impact on the development of exposure levels. A “time pattern” indicator was also derived for the non-phthalate substitute DINCH.

Care should be taken in the interpretation, since studies differ between the DEMOCOPHES survey and HBM4EU aligned studies. Also, in many cases, the countries belonging to one of the four European regions (i.e., North, East, South and West) were not identical.

Currently a “real” time trend analyses is being performed with HBM data from Denmark and Germany (Vogel et al., in preparation).

Graphs including all available studies are presented to give a general impression of median values for both periods of time; **however, a comparison of the exposure values was only performed for those countries, where studies are available for both periods of time.**

5.2 Time patterns

Phthalates used to determine the time patterns are presented in alphabetical order, followed by the non-phthalate substitute DINCH, i.e.: BBzP, DEHP (2x), DEP, DiBP, DiDP, DiNP, DnBP) and DINCH.

The full name of the parent compounds, CAS numbers and names of the metabolites are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of phthalates (in alphabetical order) and DINCH parent compounds and respective metabolites for which “time pattern” indicators have been derived

Phthalate/DINCH compounds (acronym)	full name	CAS-Number	Metabolite(s) investigated acronym	full name
BBzP	Butyl benzyl phthalate	85-68-7	MBzP	Mono-benzyl phthalate
DEHP	Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	117-81-7	5OH-MEHP	Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy- hexyl) phthalate
			5oxo-MEHP	Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxo-hexyl) phthalate
			5cx-MEPP	Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxy- pentyl) phthalate
DEP	Diethyl phthalate	84-66-2	MEP	Mono-ethyl phthalate

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 9

Phthalate/DINCH compounds (acronym)	full name	CAS-Number	Metabolite(s) investigated acronym	full name
DiBP	Di-isobutyl phthalate	84-69-5	MiBP	Mono-iso-butyl phthalate
DiDP	Di-isodecyl phthalate (all C10 phthalates including DPHP)	26761-40-0; 68515-49-1	OH-MiDP	6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate
			cx-MiDP	Mono(2,7-methyl-7- carboxy-heptyl) phthalate
DINP	Di-isononyl phthalate	28553-12-0	OH-MiNP	7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate
			cx-MiNP	7-Carboxy-(mono-methyl- heptyl) phthalate
DnBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate	84-74-2	MnBP	Mono-n-butyl phthalate
DINCH	Di-isononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate	166412-78-8	OH-MINCH	Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7- hydroxy-4-methyl)octyl ester
			cx-MINCH	Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7- carboxylate-4-methyl)heptyl ester

5.2.1 BBzP

Figure 1: Comparison of BBzP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). BBzP metabolite (MBzP) levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker MBzP in µg/L.

5.2.1.1 Interpretation

BBzP (biomarker MBzP)

The indicator (Figure 1) provides an overview of the internal exposure to BBzP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to BBzP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker MBzP are presented.

Differences in BBzP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 4.25 up to 22.12 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 5.2) and median values ranging from 1.2 up to 10.2 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 8.5).

Data from 7 countries are available for both periods of time. In these countries (i.e. DK, HU, PL, SK, SL, BE and DE) the exposure of children to BBzP was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012, based on P50

5.2.2 DEHP Σ (5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)

Figure 2: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker Σ (5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP) in $\mu\text{g/L}$. For these aggregated data no 95%-confidence intervals are available for the sum of metabolites (i.e. Σ (5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)).

Figure 3: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker 5cx-MEPP in $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure 4: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker 5OH-MEHP in µg/L.

5.2.2.1 Interpretation

Figures 2, 3 and 4

DEHP (biomarker $\sum(5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)$)

Figure 2

The indicator (Figure 2) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (biomarker $\sum(5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)$) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 6 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker $\sum(5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)$ are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 33.52 up to 62.63 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 1.9) and median values ranging from 11.63 up to 61.38 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.3).

Since the confidence intervals for the DEMOCOPHES data are not available for the sum of DEHP metabolites (i.e. $\sum(5cx-MEPP + 5OH-MEHP)$), a general comparison for the two time periods for the sum of these DEHP metabolites was not performed.

Therefore, a comparison of the single metabolites 5cx-MEPP and 5OH-MEPP between the two time periods was performed (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3

The indicator (Figure 3) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (biomarker 5cx-MEPP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 6 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 13

the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker 5cx-MEPP are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 14.55 up to 26.3 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 1.8) and median values ranging from 6.63 up to 34.99 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.3).

Data from 3 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, PL and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DEHP (biomarker cx-MEPP) was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

Figure 4

The indicator (Figure 4) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (biomarker 5OH-MEHP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker 5OH-MEHP are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 14 up to 51.25 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.7) and median values ranging from 4.98 up to 25.27 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.1).

Data from 7 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, HU, PL, SK, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DEHP (biomarker 5OH-MEHP) was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

5.2.3 DEHP Σ (5oxo-MEHP +5OH-MEHP)

Figure 5: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker Σ (5oxo-MEHP +5OH-MEHP) in $\mu\text{g/L}$. For these aggregated data no 95% confidence intervals are available for the sum of metabolites (i.e. Σ (5oxo-MEHP +5OH-MEHP)).

Figure 6: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolite levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker 5oxo-MEHP in $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure 7: Comparison of DEHP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEHP metabolite levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker 5OH-MEHP in $\mu\text{g/L}$.

5.2.3.1 Interpretation

Figures 5, 6 and 7

Figure 5

The indicator (Figure 5) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (metabolites Σ (5oxo-MEHP + 5OH-MEHP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker Σ (5oxo-MEHP + 5OH-MEHP) are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 24 up to 86.36 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.6) and median values ranging from 8.47 up to 47.58 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.6).

Since the confidence intervals for the DEMOCOPHES data are not available for the sum of DEHP metabolites (i.e. Σ (5oxo-MEHP + 5OH-MEHP)), a general comparison for the two time periods for the sum of these DEHP metabolites was not performed.

Therefore, a comparison of the single metabolites 5oxo-MEHP and 5OH-MEHP between the two time periods was performed (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6

The indicator (Figure 6) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (biomarker 5oxo-MEHP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 16

HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker 5oxo-MEHP are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 10 up to 35.1 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.5) and median values ranging from 3.44 up to 21.27 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 6.2).

Data from 7 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, HU, PL, SK, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DEHP (biomarker 5oxo-MEHP) was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

Figure 7 (identical with Figure 4)

The indicator (Figure 7) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEHP (biomarker 5OH-MEHP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEHP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker 5OH-MEHP are presented.

Differences in DEHP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 14 up to 51.25 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.7) and median values ranging from 4.98 up to 25.27 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.1).

Data from 7 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, HU, PL, SK, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DEHP (biomarker 5OH-MEHP) was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

5.2.4 DEP

Figure 8: Comparison of DEP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 11 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DEP metabolite (MEP) levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker MEP in µg/L.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 17

5.2.4.1 Interpretation

Figure 8

The indicator (Figure 8) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DEP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DEP in children from 11 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker MEP are presented.

Differences in DEP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 19.61 up to 169.2 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 8.6) and median values ranging from 6.61 up to 55.46 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 8.4).

Data from 7 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, HU, PL, SK, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DEP in DK, HU, SK and SL was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012. The exposure of children to DEP was similar in PL, BE and DE in 2014-2021 and in 2010-2012.

5.2.5 DiBP

Figure 9: Comparison of DiBP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 8 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 11 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiBP metabolite (MiBP) levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker MiBP in µg/L.

5.2.5.1 Interpretation

Figure 9

The indicator (Figure 9) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiBP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiBP in children from 8 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 11 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker MiBP are presented.

Differences in DiBP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 34.5 up to 104 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3) and median values ranging from 12.44 up to 58.85 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 4.7).

Data from 4 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DiBP was lower in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

5.2.6 DiDP

Figure 10: Comparison of DiDP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 3 studies in western Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 8 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiDP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker $\Sigma(\text{OH-MiDP} + \text{cx-MiDP})$ in µg/L. For these aggregated data no 95% confidence intervals are available for the sum of metabolites (i.e. $\Sigma(\text{OH-MiDP} + \text{cx-MiDP})$).

Figure 11: Comparison of DiDP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 3 studies in western Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 8 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiDP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker OH-MiDP in µg/L.

Figure 12: Comparison of DiDP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 3 studies in western Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 8 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiDP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker cx-MiDP in µg/L.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 20

5.2.6.1 Interpretation

Figures 10, 11 and 12

Figure 10

The indicator (Figure 10) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiDP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiDP in children from 3 western European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 8 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker $\sum(\text{OH-MiDP} + \text{cx-MiDP})$ are presented.

Differences in DiDP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 1.99 up to 3.42 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 1.7) and median values ranging from 1.12 up to 3 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 2.7).

Since the confidence intervals for the DEMOCOPHES data are not available for the sum of DiDP metabolites ($\sum(\text{OH-MiDP} + \text{cx-MiDP})$), a general comparison for the two time periods for the sum of DiDP metabolites was not performed.

Therefore, a comparison of the single metabolites OH-MiDP and cx-MiDP between the two time periods was performed (Figures 6b and 6c).

Figure 11

The indicator (Figure 11) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiDP (metabolite OH-DiDP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiDP in children from 3 western European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 11 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker OH-MiDP are presented.

Differences in DiDP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 0.61 up to 2.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.3) and median values ranging from 0.52 up to 2.78 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.3).

Data from 2 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e., BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DiDP (biomarker OH-MiDP) was similar in BE in 2014-2021 and 2010-2012 and lower in DE in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

Figure 12

The indicator (Figure 12) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiDP (metabolite cx-MiDP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiDP in children from 3 western European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 8 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker cx-MiDP are presented.

Differences in DiDP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 1.08 up to 1.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 1.3) and median values ranging from 0.51 up to 1.15 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 2.3).

Data from 2 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e., BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DiDP (biomarker cx-DiDP) was similar DE in 2014-2021 and 2010-2012 and lower in BE in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

5.2.7 DiNP

Figure 13: Comparison of DiNP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 10 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiNP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker ($\sum(\text{OH-MiNP} + \text{cx-MiNP})$ in $\mu\text{g/L}$). For these aggregated data no 95% confidence intervals are available for the sum of metabolites (i.e. $\sum(\text{OH-MiNP} + \text{cx-MiNP})$).

Figure 14: Comparison of DiNP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 8 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 10 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiNP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker cx-MiNP in $\mu\text{g/L}$.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 22

Figure 15: Comparison of DiNP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 10 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DiNP metabolites levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker OH-MiNP in µg/L.

5.2.7.1 Interpretation

Figure 13, 14 and 15

Figure 13

The indicator (Figure 13) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiNP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiNP in children from 6 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 10 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker ($\sum(\text{OH-MiNP} + \text{cx-MiNP})$), are presented.

Differences in DiNP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 7.9 up to 28.89 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 3.7) and median values ranging from 2.49 up to 17.77 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 7.1).

Since the confidence intervals for the DEMOCOPHES data are not available for the sum of DiNP metabolites (i.e. ($\sum(\text{OH-MiNP} + \text{cx-MiNP})$), a general comparison for the two time periods for the sum of these DiNP metabolites was not performed.

Therefore, a comparison of the single metabolites cx-MiNP and OH-MiNP between the two time periods was performed (Figures 7b and c).

Figure 14

The indicator (Figure 14) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiNP (biomarker cx-MiNP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiNP in children from 8 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 23

the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 10 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker cx-MiNP are presented.

Differences in DiNP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 1.21 up to 19.91 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 16.5) and median values ranging from 0.28 up to 10.4 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 37.1).

Data from 4 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, PL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DiNP (biomarker cx-MiNP) was lower in 3 of these 4 countries in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012. The exposure was similar in PL.

Figure 15

The indicator (Figure 15) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DiNP (biomarker OH-MiNP) in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DiNP in children from 6 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 10 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker OH-MiNP are presented.

Differences in DiNP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 4.99 up to 12.52 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 2.5) and median values ranging from 1.9 up to 7.75 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 4.1).

Data from 3 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e., DK, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to MiNP (biomarker OH-MiNP) was lower in 2014-2021.

5.2.8 DnBP

Figure 16: Comparison of DnBP exposure in children (6-11 years) from 8 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DnBP metabolites (M_nBP) levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker M_nBP in µg/L.

5.2.8.1 Interpretation

Figure 16

The indicator (Figure 16) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DnBP in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DnBP in children from 8 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 12 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) for the biomarker DnBP values are presented.

Differences in DnBP exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 31 up to 82.5 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 2.7) and median values ranging from 12.73 up to 74.77 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 5.9).

Data from 5 countries are available for both periods of time (i.e. DK, PL, SL, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DnBP was lower in 4 of these 5 countries in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012. Based on P50, the exposure of children was similar in BE in 2014-2021 and 2010-2012.

5.2.9 DINCH

Figure 17: Comparison of DINCH exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 11 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DINCH metabolite levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker Σ (OH-MINCH + cx-MINCH) in $\mu\text{g/L}$. For these aggregated data no 95% confidence intervals are available for the sum of metabolites (i.e. OH-MINCH + cx-MINCH).

Figure 18: Comparison of DINCH exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 12 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DINCH metabolite levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker OH-MINCH in $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure 19: Comparison of DINCH exposure in children (6-11 years) from 6 studies in Europe between 2010-2012 (DEMOCOPHES survey) and 11 studies in children in Europe between 2014-2021 (HBM4EU aligned studies). DINCH metabolite levels were either measured in first morning or random spot urine samples. Columns show P50 for the biomarker cx-MINCH in µg/L.

5.2.9.1 Interpretation

Figures 17, 18 and 19

Figure 17

The indicator (Figure 17) provides an overview of the internal exposure to DINCH in children (6-11 years) during two specific periods in time. It shows differences of exposure to DINCH in children from 6 European countries from data of the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 and the exposure from 11 European countries conducted under the HBM4EU aligned studies between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values for the biomarker (\sum (OH-MINCH + cx-MINCH)) are presented.

Differences in DINCH exposure between the studies can be observed with median values ranging from 1.35 up to 2.23 µg/L in the DEMOCOPHES survey (values varied by a factor of 1.7) and median values ranging from 1.94 up to 5.35 µg/L in the HBM4EU aligned studies (values varied by a factor of 2.8).

Since the confidence intervals for the DEMOCOPHES data are not available for the sum of DINCH metabolites (i.e. (\sum (OH-MINCH + cx-MINCH))), a general comparison for the two time periods for the sum of these DINCH metabolites was not performed.

Therefore, a comparison of the single metabolites OH-MINCH and cx-MINCH between the two time periods was performed (Figure 18 and Figure 19).

Figures 18 and 19

The indicator (Figure 18 and Figure 19) provides an overview of the internal exposure towards DINCH in children (6-11 years) in two specific periods in time. It compares DINCH (i.e. OH-MINCH and cx-MINCH) levels analysed in 6 European countries under the DEMOCOPHES survey (2010-2012) with analyses from 12 (OH-MINCH) and 11 (cx-MINCH) countries, respectively, which took

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 27

part in the HBM4EU aligned studies in children conducted between 2014-2021. Median (P50) values are presented.

Differences in DINCH levels between the studies can be observed:

Median values for the metabolite OH-MINCH varied by a factor of 1.5 in the DEMOCOPHES survey and by a factor of 2.9 in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Median values for cx-MINCH varied by a factor of 2.6 in the DEMOCOPHES studies and by a factor of 4.2 in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

cx-MINCH

Data for both periods of time are available from 3 countries (i.e., DK, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DINCH (biomarker cx-MINCH) was higher in DK and DE 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012. The exposure was similar in BE in 2014-2021 and 2010-2012.

OH-MINCH

Data for both periods of time are available from 3 countries (i.e., DK, BE and DE). Based on P50, the exposure of children to DINCH (biomarker OH-MINCH) was higher in 2014-2021 compared to 2010-2012.

This is in accordance with data from the literature, where increasing time trends of DINCH exposure are reported (e.g. Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. (2019), Lemke et al. (2021) and Schwedler et al. (2020b). Lemke et al. (2021) reported that substitutes mimic the exposure behaviour of REACH regulated phthalates. Therefore, increasing regulations of certain phthalates lead to a decrease in measured concentrations of these compounds. Concurrently, a shift to non-regulated phthalates or substitutes (such as DINCH) takes place, leading to an increase of measured concentrations for these substitutes.

General findings from the literature concerning time trends of phthalate exposure:

Schwedler et al. (2020) compared samples from the German Environmental Survey (GerES) collected in the years 2015-2017 (GerES V) with samples from 2002-2006 (GerES IV) and found considerably lower phthalate metabolite levels at the later time point for all phthalates considered in both studies (i.e., BBzP, MnBP, DEHP, DiBP and DiNP). The highest difference was found for BBzP (metabolite MBzP).

Frederiksen et al. (2020) investigated human exposure in young Danish men from 2009-2017. The authors found a significant decrease in urinary concentrations over time. Median concentrations of the metabolites of BBzP, DEHP, DiBP and DnBP more than halved from 2009-2017.

Also, Koch et al. (2017) and Apel et al. (2020) who examined time trends of phthalate exposure from samples of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) from 1988 to 2015 found decreasing phthalate concentrations in time for the metabolites investigated.

An HBM4EU data analyses from Danish and German time trend studies is currently being performed (Vogel et al.in preparation).

Reasons for the observed decline are seen in political measures being effective for the regulated phthalates.

The reason for the decline of the less regulated phthalates is presumably due to a decreased production/application of these substances in response to the proposed future regulations for these substances expected by the producers.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 28

However, it should be noted, that despite decreasing phthalate metabolite levels, they are still a health concern in Europe as results from HBM4EU aligned studies have shown (see DELIVERABLE AD5.6 impact indicators for phthalates).

5.3 TAB methodology

5.3.1 Definition

HBM4EU aligned studies

50th percentile; median (P50) concentrations of metabolites of selected phthalates (i.e. BBzP, DnBP, DiBP, DEHP, DiNP, DEP, DiDP) and DINCH were measured in urine samples obtained from a sample of children 6-11 years (general population) in a given study area (see locations below), obtained between 2014-2021.

DEMOCOPHES survey

50th percentile; median (P50) concentrations of metabolites of selected phthalates (i.e. BBzP, DnBP, DiBP, DEHP, DiNP, DEP, DiDP) and DINCH were measured in urine samples from a sample of children (6-11 years) in a given study area (see locations below), obtained between 2010-2012.

5.3.2 Disaggregation

Place of residence:

HBM4EU aligned studies for children (6-11 years)

Data considered for the comparison of time periods

BBzP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DEHP:

5xc-MEPP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

5OH-MEHP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

5oxo-MEHP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DEP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DiBP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DiDP:

OH-MiDP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), The Netherlands (NL)

cx-MiDP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), The Netherlands (NL)

DiNP:

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 29

OH-MiNP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), The Netherlands (NL)

cx-MiNP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), The Netherlands (NL)

DnBP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DINCH:

OH-MINCH: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Norway (NO), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

cx-MINCH: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Italy (IT), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Slovakia (SK), The Netherlands (NL)

DEMOCOPHES survey

Data considered for the comparison of time periods

BBzP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Hungary (HU), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Slovakia (SK), Slovenia (SL), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE)

DEHP:

5xc-MEPP: Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Sweden (SE);

5OH-MEHP: Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Sweden (SE);

5oxo-MEHP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Hungary (HU), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Slovakia (SK), Slovenia (SL), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE);

DEP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Hungary (HU), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Slovakia (SK), Slovenia (SL), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE);

DiBP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Spain (ES);

DiDP:

OH-MiDP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), Luxembourg (LU)

cx-MiDP: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), Luxembourg (LU)

DiNP:

OH-MiNP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Sweden (SE);

cx-MiNP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE);

DnBP: Belgium (BE), Czech Republic (CZ), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Poland (PL), Slovenia (SL), Spain (ES);

DINCH:

OH-MINCH: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE).

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 30

cx-MINCH: Belgium (BE), Denmark (DK), Germany (DE), Luxembourg (LU), Spain (ES), Sweden (SE).

5.3.3 Method of measurement

HBM4EU aligned studies

50th percentile; median (P50) concentrations of metabolites of selected phthalates (i.e. BBzP, DEHP, DEP, DiBP, DiDP, DiNP, DnBP) and DINCH were measured in urine samples obtained from a sample of children 6-11 years (general population) in a given study area (see locations above), obtained between 2014-2021.

DEMOCOPHES survey

50th percentile; median (P50) concentrations of metabolites of selected phthalates (i.e. BBzP, DEHP, DEP, DiBP, DiDP, DiNP, DnBP) and DINCH were measured in urine samples from a sample of children (6-11 years) in a given study area (see locations above), obtained between 2010-2012.

5.3.4 Method of estimation

P50 (50th percentile; median): 50% of the participants had a concentration value equal or below this value.

The included studies are not representative for their country but do include inhabitants from urban, semi-urban and rural areas and a 50:50 male:female ratio. The study areas were not considered as hot spot areas for phthalates and DINCH.

5.4 TAB additional information

5.4.1 Monitoring assessment

Phthalates are a group of industrial chemicals that are widely used as plasticisers to make plastics flexible. They are used in a wide range of consumer products including vinyl flooring, food contact materials, personal care products and children's toys.

Some phthalates are banned in Europe. DINCH is a non-phthalate which has been put on the market in 2002 as a substitute for some of the most toxic phthalates.

There are a number of ways that people can be exposed to phthalates, among them: consuming food and drinks that have been held in phthalate containing containers. They can also be taken up via the skin by the use of certain personal care products. Children can be exposed due to their specific behaviour like sucking on plastic toys containing phthalates or their hand-to-mouth behaviour which leads to dust containing phthalates to enter their bodies.

Once phthalates enter the human body, they are broken down into metabolites and pass out of the body rather quickly in urine. Phthalate metabolite levels in human urine are representative of the exposure to the respective parent compounds that occurred within the last 24 hours (Koch and Calafat, 2009). Due to the regular exposure to phthalates over time, persons are exposed on a continuous basis to phthalates regardless the short half-life.

5.4.2 Health impact assessment

Certain phthalates are toxic and can contribute to a number of chronic diseases (EFSA, 2019). Exposure to some phthalates (i.e. DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, DiBP and DiNP) is associated with reproductive effects in humans. This means that they can damage human fertility and cause harm to the unborn child. Some phthalates are known to affect the hormonal system, they are endocrine

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 31

disruptors. Recent studies conducted under HBM4EU reported a possible link between phthalate exposure and asthma (Mattila et al., 2021), osteoporosis (Elonheimo et al., 2021), metabolic syndrome (Haverinen et al., 2021) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Moore et al., 2022).

Within HBM4EU age-dependent HBM-GVs (human biomonitoring guidance values) have been derived for 5 phthalates and DINCH for the general population for the two groups:

1. children (6-13 years) and
2. adolescents, adults (from 14 years onwards) (Lange et al., 2021).

The HBM-GV values for the phthalates investigated are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: HBM-GVs derived within HBM4EU for the phthalates under consideration and DINCH (Lange et al., 2021)

Parent compound	Full name	CAS-No.	Metabolite(s)	HBM-GV _{GenPop} in µg/L	
				children	adolescents/adults
BBzP	Benzyl butyl phthalate	85-68-7	MBzP	20000	3000
DEHP	Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate	117-81-7	Σ (5-oxo + 5-OH-MEHP)	340	500
			Σ (5-cx-MEPP + 5-OH-MEHP)	380	570
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate	84-69-5	MiBP	160	230
DnBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate	84-74-2	MnBP	120	190
DINCH	Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate	166412-78-8	Σ (OH-MINCH + cx-MINCH)	3000	4500

For DEP (full name: Diethyl phthalate, CAS-No: 84-66-2) a BE (biomonitoring equivalent) value of 18000 µg/L exists. This has been taken for a comparison with P95 values of the metabolite MEP.

Impact indicators comparing P95 exposure levels with the corresponding HBM-GVs (BE value in the case of DEP) have been derived in Additional Deliverable AD5.6 for DiBP and DINCH. Impact indicators for BBzP, DEP, DEHP and DnBP have also been derived and will be presented on the HBM4EU website.

5.4.3 EU-level assessment

Policy relevance

As already mentioned in AD5.6, phthalates are a cause of concern as several have been shown to adversely impact reproductive and potentially other functions and are known to be frequently encountered by humans. Indeed, a number of phthalates have been classified as toxic to reproduction (Repr. 1B under the CLP).

While some of the phthalates are considered to be SVHC, some phthalates like DMP and the non-phthalate substitute DINCH have no classified health effects.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 32

In addition, some phthalates (BBzP, DnBP, DCHP, DEHP and DiBP) are specifically classified by ECHA for their endocrine disruption properties although the pharmacological mechanisms responsible vary from chemical to chemical (for example, some show oestrogenic activity whilst others act as anti-androgens).

BBzP, DnBP, DiBP and DEHP are classified as reproductive toxicants category 1B under Annex VI to the Classification Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation (EC 1272/2008). This is also the case for DnPeP, DiPeP, DHNUP, DnHP and DMEP. These are the other phthalates covered in HBM4EU, but for which no indicators are provided.

In addition to their reprotoxic properties, DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, and BBzP also have endocrine disrupting properties and have been classified as SVHC (Annex XIV EC 1907/2006) and are therefore included in the candidate list for the inclusion in Annex XIV of the REACH regulation (Annex XIV of REACH EC 1907/2006). Four of the nine above mentioned phthalates have already been subject to authorisation (Directive (EU) 2015/863) since February 2015, namely DEHP, BBzP, DiBP and DnBP. Since February 2015 they must not be used within the European Union without authorisation. Since July 2020, DiPeP, DHNUP, DMEP, DnPeP and DnHP are also subject to authorisation.

To a certain extent, the current restrictions under REACH also cover some phthalates. Reprotoxic substances, such as DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, DiBP, DnPeP, DiPeP, DCHP, DHNUP, DnHP and DMEP are generally not allowed to be placed on the market, in the EU for supply to the general public as individual substances or in mixtures when their concentrations are equal to or exceed 0,3%.

In addition, DiNP, di-n-octyl phthalate (DnOP), and DiDP are restricted for all children's toys and childcare articles that can be placed in children's mouth with a concentration limit of 0.1 % by entry 52 of Annex XVII to REACH. Entry 51 of Annex XVII to REACH, also restricts DEHP, DBP, BBP and DiBP in toys or childcare articles, in a concentration equal to or greater than 0,1 % by weight of the plasticised material.

In July 2020, a further restriction on DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, and BBzP took effect, which states that the above-mentioned phthalates are restricted to a concentration equal to or below 0.1% by weight individually or in any combination in any plasticised material in articles used by consumers or in indoor areas (EC 2018).

In addition to the REACH legislation, there are also product-specific legislations which regulate certain phthalates. These include the Cosmetic Products' Regulation (EC/1223/2009) and the regulation on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food (EC 1935/2004 and Directives 80/590/ECC & 89/109/ECC) or, more specifically the Regulation for Plastics Implementation Measure (10/2011/EC).

5.5 TAB references

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AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 33

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AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 34

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6 Pesticide indicator

6.1 Information

Data source: HBM4EU data are obtained from <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>, data consulted on 5th of April 2022. However, this data is not yet publicly available on the website.

6.1.1 Geographical differences indicator

Glyphosate and AMPA

Figure 20: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of glyphosate from 5 studies in children (6-11 years) and 4 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ORGANIKO, SLO CRP, DIET-HBM, ESB and HBM4EU study), LOD = 0.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ESTEBAN).

Figure 21: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of AMPA from 5 studies in children (6-11 years) and 4 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (SLO CRP, GerES V, DIET-HBM, ESB), LOQ = 0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (3xG and HBM4EU study).

Chlorpyrifos (TCPy)

Figure 22: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of TCPy from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) and 6 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOD = 0.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ESTEBAN). TCPy is a marker of chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl. note: TCPy data from France were analysed in a laboratory that did not participate in HBM4EU QA/QC scheme.

Pyrethroids

Figure 23: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value 3-PBA (non-specific marker of Cyhalothrin, cypermethrin, deltamethrin, fenpropathrin, permethrin, tralomethrin) from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) and 5 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021.

Figure 24: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value 4-F-3-PBA (Cyfluthrin biomarker) from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) and 5 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ORGANIKO, 3xG, RAV MABAT, DIET-HBM, ESB, HBM4EU study), LOQ = 0.015 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ESTEBAN), LOD = 0.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (SLO CRP), LOD = 0.03 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (SPECIMEn-NL).

Figure 25: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of $\Sigma(\text{cis-DCCA} + \text{trans-DCCA})$ from 5 studies in children (6-11 years) and 5 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. $\Sigma(\text{cis-DCCA} + \text{trans-DCCA})$ are metabolites of cyfluthrin, permethrin, and cypermethrin

Figure 26: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of cis-DBCA (marker for deltamethrin) from 5 studies in children (6-11 years) and 5 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ESB).

Figure 27: Exposure indicator showing median (P50) value and P95 value of CIF3CA from 4 studies in children (6-11 years) and 4 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021. LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (ORGANIKO, 3xG, ESB and HBM4EU study Cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid (CIF3CA) is a biomarker for bifenthrin, (lambda)cyclohalothrin and tefluthrin.

6.1.2 Health impact indicator

Chlorpyrifos

Figure 28: Indicator showing P95 value of TCPy (biomarker of chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl) from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) and 6 studies in adults (20-39 years) in Europe between 2014-2021 compared to the provisional HBM-GV for non-cancer end-points (children 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$, adults 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (y-axis: logarithmic scale). The graph is based on data from the HBM4EU Aligned studies in children (Cyprus: ORGANIKO, Slovenia: SLO CRP, Belgium: 3xG, France: ESTEBAN, The Netherlands: SPECIMEn-NL, Israel: RAV-MABAT). ESTEBAN LOD = 0.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$. note: TCPy data from France were analysed in a laboratory that did not participate in HBM4EU QA/QC scheme.

Pyrethroids

Figure 29: Indicator showing P95 value of 3-PBA (marker for pyrethroids) from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) in Europe between 2014-2021 compared to the Tier 1 Biomonitoring equivalent value (BE-value) of 1.7 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and Tier 2 BE-value of 87 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (y-axis: logarithmic scale). The graph is based on data from the HBM4EU Aligned studies in children (Cyprus: ORGANIKO, Slovenia: SLO CRP, Belgium: 3xG, France: ESTEBAN, The Netherlands: SPECIMEn-NL, Israel: RAV-MABAT) and the HBM4EU Aligned studies in adults (Iceland: DIET-HBM, France: ESTEBAN, Germany: ESB, Switzerland: HBM4EU-study, Israel: RAV-MABAT).

Figure 30: Indicator showing P95 value of 4-F-3-PBA (marker for cyfluthrin) from 6 studies in children (6-11 years) in Europe between 2014-2021 compared to the Biomonitoring equivalent value (BE-value) of 46 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and HBM-GV of 80 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for children and 130 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in adults (y-axis: logarithmic scale). The graph is based on data from the HBM4EU Aligned studies in children (Cyprus: ORGANIKO, Slovenia: SLO CRP, Belgium: 3xG, France: ESTEBAN, The Netherlands: SPECIMEn-NL, Israel: RAV-MABAT) and the HBM4EU Aligned studies in adults (Iceland: DIET-HBM, France: ESTEBAN, Germany: ESB, Switzerland: HBM4EU-study, Israel: RAV-MABAT). LOQ = 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (CY, BE, DE, CH), LOD = 0.03 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (NL) and LOD = 0.035 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (IL).

Figure 31: Indicator showing P95 value of cis-DBCA (marker for Deltamethrin) from 5 studies in children (6-11 years) in Europe between 2014-2021 compared to the available health based guidance values (BE-value 20 µg/L and HBM-GV of 90 µg/L in children and 130 µg/L in adults) (y-axis: logarithmic scale). The graph is based on data from the HBM4EU Aligned studies in children (Cyprus: ORGANIKO, Belgium: 3xG, France: ESTEBAN, The Netherlands: SPECIMEN-NL, Israel: RAV-MABAT) and the HBM4EU Aligned studies in adults (Iceland: DIET-HBM, France: ESTEBAN, Germany: ESB, Switzerland: HBM4EU-study, Israel: RAV-MABAT).

6.2 TAB time pattern

Time patterns not available.

6.3 Interpretation

6.3.1 Geographical differences indicator

The indicator (Figure 20) provides an overview of glyphosate concentration levels in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries, sampled between 2014-2021. In most sampling locations median values are below LOD/LOQ. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 1.7 between sampling sites in children. P95 values differ up to a factor 4 between sampling sites. P95 observed for glyphosate are higher in children than in adults. P95 values children are a factor 4 higher than the median values.

The indicator (Figure 21) provides an overview of AMPA concentration levels in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries, sampled between 2014-2021. AMPA is the main metabolite of glyphosate but there is also a contribution of other sources (use of amino-polyphosphonate in industry and household and through contaminated food items). In most sampling locations median values are below LOD/LOQ. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 1.2 between sampling sites in children. P95 values differ up to a factor 2.2 between sampling sites. P95 observed for AMPA are higher in children than in adults. In children and adults P95 are a factor 3 higher than median values.

The indicator (Figure 22) provides an overview of TCPy (exposure biomarker of chlorpyrifos pesticide) concentration levels in urine samples of children and adults from 9 European countries and Israel, sampled between 2014-2021. Study specific differences in median values up to a factor 10.9 and 4.7 can be observed in children and adults respectively. P95 values differ up to a factor

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 44

4.8 and 3.3 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 are a factor 1.9-8 higher than P50.

The indicator (Figure 23) provides an overview of 3-PBA (biomarker for pyrethroids in general) in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 2.8 and 3.3 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 values differ up to a factor 2.1 and 4.1 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. Furthermore, median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values are a factor 2.5-6 higher than median values.

The indicator (Figure 24) provides an overview of 4-F-3-PBA (biomarker for pyrethroids) in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021. Median values are all < LOD/LOQ in children and adults. P95 values in adults are all below LOD/LOQ except for France. In children, P95 values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 3.1 between sampling sites.

The indicator (Figure 25) provides an overview of the sum of cis-DCCA + trans-DCCA (metabolites of pyrethroids cypermethrin, cyfluthrin, permethrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 2 and 1.7 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 values differ up to a factor 2.4 and 1.7 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. Median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values a factor 3-6 higher than median values.

The indicator (Figure 26) provides an overview of cis-DBCA (biomarker for deltamethrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 6 and 5.5 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 values differ up to a factor 5.8 and 15 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. Median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values a factor 2-7 higher than median values.

The indicator (Figure 27) provides an overview of CIF3CA (biomarker for bifenthrin, (lambda)cylhalothrin and tefluthrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 5 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021. For most of the studies median values are below the LOD/LOQ. Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 1.25 between sampling sites in children. P95 values differ up to a factor 3.9 and 2 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 values a factor 4-7 higher than median values.

6.3.2 Health impact indicator

The indicator (Figure 28) illustrates P95 levels of TCPy (exposure biomarker of chlorpyrifos pesticide) in children and adults from 9 European countries and Israel compared to the available health based guidance values. For TCPy provisional HBM-GV are derived for children and adults (*Tarazona et al. 2022*). Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU in children exceed the provisional HBM-GV for non-cancer endpoints 10 µg/L in 2 sampling locations (CY, IL), in adults P95 concentrations are all below provisional HBM-GV of 20 µg/L. However, it should be noted that these provisional HBM-GV are not fully protective because of genotoxicity (*Tarazona et al. 2022*).

The indicator (Figure 29) illustrates P95 levels of 3-PBA (general marker for pyrethroids) in children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel compared to the available health based guidance values. For 3-PBA, two BE-values were derived by Aylward et al. for tiered interpretation of HBM exposure levels in risk assessment context. A highly conservative tier 1 screening value of 1.7 µg/L which assumes that all the pesticides that metabolise to 3-PBA have a high toxic potency and a

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 45

second-tier screening value of 87 µg/L which assumes average toxic potency of the pesticide mixture, to be used when HBM data exceed the Tier 1 value (Aylward et al. 2018). Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU exceed the conservative tier 1 (BE-value of 1.7 µg/L) in all sampling sites in children and in 3/5 sampling sites in adults. All P95 values are well below the tier 2 BE-value of 87 µg/L.

The indicator (Figure 30) illustrates P95 levels of 4-F-3-PBA (marker for cyfluthrin) in children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel compared to the available health based guidance values (BE-value 46 µg/L and HBM-GV of 80 µg/L in children and 130 µg/L in adults). Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU lay a factor 219 lower than the BE-value of 46 µg/L and a factor 380 lower than the HBM-GV in children and a factor 1857 lower in adults. The concentrations were thus clearly lower than the BE and HBM-GV values indicating that according to the current knowledge there is no risk for adverse health effects.

The indicator (Figure 31) illustrates P95 levels of cis-DBCA (marker for Deltamethrin) in children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel with respect to the available health-based guidance values (BE-value 20 µg/L and HBM-GV of 90 µg/L in children and 130 µg/L in adults).

Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU lay a factor 3.7 lower than the BE-value of 20 µg/L and a factor 16.9 lower than the HBM-GV in children and a factor 24 lower than the HBM-GV in adults. The concentrations were thus lower than the BE and HBM-GV values indicating that according to the current knowledge there is no risk for adverse health effects.

6.4 TAB methodology

6.4.1 Definition

50th percentile/median (P50) and 95th percentile (P95) pesticide concentration measured in urine samples obtained from a sample of children and adults (general population) in a given study area (see location below), obtained between 2014-2021. The pesticide concentrations are standardised for urinary dilution by dividing the volume-based pesticide concentrations (µg/L) by creatinine measured in the same urine sample (g creatinine/L). The resulting pesticide concentrations are expressed in µg/g creatinine. For comparison with human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GV) or Biomonitoring equivalent value (BE-value), the µg/L scale was used in compliance with the units of the HBM-GV and BE-value. Limit of detection (LOD), Limit of quantification (LOQ).

6.4.2 Disaggregation

Country in which the sampling site is located: Cyprus (CY), Slovenia (SI), Belgium (BE), France (FR), The Netherlands (NL) and Israel (IL) for the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in children and Iceland (IS), Portugal (PT), France (FR), Germany (DE), Switzerland (CH) and Israel (IL) for the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults.

6.4.3 Method of measurement

Chemical analysis of the biomarkers was quality controlled, except for the data from ESTEBAN (TCPy, glyphosate, Trans-DCCA), SO CRP (TCPy, glyphosate, 4-F-3-PBA), ESB (glyphosate) and INSEF-ExpoQuim (TCPy) which were analysed by a laboratory that did not participate in the HBM4EU QA/QC scheme.

6.4.4 Method of estimation

P50 (50th percentile): 50% of the participants had a concentration value equal or below this value.

P95 (95th percentile): 95% of the participants had a concentration value equal or below this value.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 46

The included studies are not representative for their country but do include inhabitants from urban, semi-urban and rural areas and a 50:50 male:female ratio. The study areas were not considered as hot spot areas for pesticides.

Table 3: HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults for which data is presented in the graphs

Study name	Number of individuals	Sex	Age range	Sampling period	Biological sample	Area of sample collection
DIET_HBM	170	men and women	20 - 39y	2019-2021	Random spot urine	Iceland
ESTEBAN	169	men and women	20 - 39y	2014-2016	first morning urine	Mainland France
INSEF-ExpoQuim	295	men and women	28 – 39y	2019-2020	first morning urine	Portugal
ESB	250	men and women	20 - 29y	2014-2021	24h urine	Münster, Greifswald, Halle/Saale and Ulm region (Germany)
HBM4EU-study Switzerland	300	men and women	20 - 39y	2020	first morning urine	Basel (Switzerland)
RAV MABAT	83	men and women	23-39y	2015-2016	Random spot urine	Israel

Table 4: The HBM4EU Aligned Studies in children for which data is presented in the graphs

Study name	Number of individuals	Sex	Age range	Sampling period	Biological sample	Area of sample collection
ORGANIKO	166	boys and girls	10-11y	2017	first morning urine	Limassol (Cyprus)
SLO CRP	149	boys and girls	7-11y	2018	first morning urine	Mura region (Slovenia)
3XG	133	boys and girls	6-8y	2019-2021	first morning urine	Dessel, Mol, Retie (Belgium)
ESTEBAN	223	boys and girls	6-11y	2014-2016	first morning urine	Mainland France
GerES V	300	boys and girls	6-11y	2015-2017	first morning urine	Germany

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 47

Study name	Number of individuals	Sex	Age range	Sampling period	Biological sample	Area of sample collection
SPECIMEN-NL	102	boys and girls	6-11y	2020	Random spot urine	Central-East Netherlands
RAV MABAT	94		6-11y	2015-2016	Random spot urine	Israel

6.5 TAB additional information

6.5.1 Monitoring assessment

Pesticides are monitored under HBM4EU as a group and include pyrethroids (group), chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, glyphosate (including the co-formulant POE-tallow amine) and fipronil.

Diet is the main pathway of intake for several of these chemical groups, and as such, HBM4EU is generating valuable evidence of immediate relevance to the “Farm to Fork” strategy. HBM4EU can also inform on the relative weight of the different exposure routes which is valuable in pesticide hot spot areas.

As mentioned in the European Commission’s roadmap for the [Farm to Fork Strategy](#), the current food system needs to be changed to significantly reduce the use of pesticides and fertilisers and the related environmental and human health risks.

6.5.2 Health impact assessment

Urinary concentrations of metabolites were compared with new HBM-GV (human biomonitoring guidance) values derived within HBM4EU and with existing BE-values (biomonitoring equivalents). Within HBM4EU, HBM-GV were derived as “the concentration of a substance in human biological material below which – according to the knowledge and judgement of the HBM4EU consortium– there is no risk for adverse health effects. BE-values are defined as “the concentration or range of concentrations of a chemical or its metabolite in a biological medium (blood, urine, or other medium) that is consistent with an existing health-based exposure guideline”.

For chlorpyrifos (TCPy), provisional HBM-GV for non-cancer endpoints of 10 µg/L (children) and 20 µg/L (adults) has been derived by the HBM4EU consortium (Tarazona et al. 2022). It should be noted that these provisional HBM-GV are not fully protective because of genotoxicity. Provisional HBM-GV for genotox/carcinogenicity of 1 µg/L (children) and 2 µg/L (adults) were derived which is based on a threshold mode of action. For more information see Tarazona et al (2022).

For 3-PBA, a general marker for pyrethroids) two BE-values were derived by Aylward et al. for tiered interpretation of HBM exposure levels in risk assessment context. A highly conservative tier 1 screening value of 1.7 µg/L which assumes that all the pesticides that metabolise to 3-PBA have a high toxic potency and a second tier screening value of 87 µg/L which assumes average toxic potency of the pesticide mixture, to be used when HBM data exceed the Tier 1 value (Aylward et al. 2018).

For Deltametrin (DBCA), a BE-value 20 µg/L is set for individuals 6 years and older by Health Canada (Aylward et al. 2011). In 2022 a human biomonitoring guidance value (HBM-GV) of 90 µg/L in urine of children and 130 µg/L in urine of adults has been derived by the HBM4EU

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 48

consortium (not yet published). The value of the HBM-GV was based on a study on neurotoxicity observed in rats and dogs (ECHA 2011; EFSA 2018).

For Cyfluthrin (biomarker 4-F-3-PBA), a BE-value 46 µg/L is set for individuals 6 years and older by Health Canada (Hays et al. 2009). In 2022, an HBM-GV of 80 µg/L in urine of children and 130 µg/L in urine of adults has been derived by the HBM4EU consortium (not yet published). The value of the HBM-GV was based on a study on acute neurotoxicity effects observed in rats (EC 2020).

6.5.3 EU-level assessment

Several policy measures have already been introduced in the EU to address human exposure to pesticides and managing risks.

The latest policy is the [Farm to Fork Strategy](#) embedded in the European Green Deal which includes the target to reduce the use of chemicals and more hazardous pesticides by 50 % until 2030. Further, the Commission aims to promote evidence-based policymaking on pesticides by overcoming data gaps. In general, the existing EU policies cover regulations on chemicals, consumer products, the environment and occupational exposure.

On chemicals, part of the pesticides considered in HBM4EU are subject to [Regulation \(EC\) 1107/2009](#) on placing plant protection products on the market. They are also subject to [Regulation \(EU\) 528/2012](#) on making available on the market and use of biocidal products.

The pesticides' registration and registered uses, are considered registered under [Regulation \(EC\) No 1907/2006](#) on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). Applicants do not need to submit a separate dossier under REACH unless they have uses outside of the scope of biocides/pesticides.

In April 2022, 22 additional chemicals were added to [PIC](#) (Prior Informed Consent). Of those, 15 were pesticides and seven industrial chemicals, including all substances containing benzene as a constituent in concentrations above 0.1 % weight by weight. The PIC regulation includes dimethoate, and the pyrethroids allethrin and cypermethrin.

As well as the export notification, most of these chemicals will also require an explicit consent from the importing country before exports can take place.

On the environment, the [Drinking Water Directive \(98/83/EC\)](#) limits the concentration of individual pesticides in water for public consumption to 0.1 µg/L. The sum of all individual pesticides detected is limited to 0.5 µg/L. [Regulation \(EU\) 649/2012](#) which lists chemicals subject to export notification procedure, includes the pyrethroids permethrin and fenpropathrin.

On consumer products, maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin (e.g., 10 mg/kg wheat) are regulated under [Regulation \(EC\) 396/2005](#).

Pesticide residues in infant and follow-on formulae are subject to [Directive 2006/141/EC](#). The standard maximum residue level (MRL) is set to 0.01 mg/kg, whereas specific MRLs for certain pesticides are defined as well (e.g., fipronil 0.004 mg/kg).

On occupational, the reduction of risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment is regulated under [Directive 2009/128/EC](#) on sustainable use of pesticides. This comprises e.g., the inspection of equipment in use and training for professional users.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 49

6.6 TAB contact

A contact tab could be added, for additional requests on information. Please see below an example.

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AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 50

7 Conclusions

Phthalates

For phthalates, the analysis and conclusions have been thoroughly described in section 5.

Within HBM4EU, age-dependent HBM-GVs (human biomonitoring guidance values) have been derived for 5 phthalates and DINCH for the general population for the two groups:

1. children (6-13 years) and
2. adolescents, adults (from 14 years onwards) (Lange et al., 2021).

The HBM-GV values for the phthalates investigated are presented in Table 2.

Impact indicators comparing P95 exposure levels with the corresponding HBM-GVs (BE value in the case of DEP) have been derived in Additional Deliverable AD5.6 for DiBP and DINCH.

Impact indicators for BBzP, DEP, DEHP and DnBP have also been derived and will be presented on the HBM4EU website - a HBM4EU data analyses from Danish and German time trend studies is currently being performed (Vogel et al.in preparation).

Overall, there is a decline in phthalate exposure in the European population.

This may be due to restrictions being put in place which helped to reduce phthalate exposure for regulated phthalates.

The reason for the decline of the less regulated phthalates is presumably due to a decreased production/application of these substances in response to the proposed future regulations for these substances expected by the producers.

However, it should be noted, that despite decreasing phthalate metabolite levels, they are still a health concern in Europe as results from HBM4EU aligned studies have shown (see DELIVERABLE AD5.6 impact indicators for phthalates).

Pesticides:

Glyphosate concentrations in children and adults (

Figure 20) from 7 European countries, sampled between 2014-2021, show:

- median values are below LOD/LOQ.
- P95 observed for glyphosate are higher in children than in adults.
- P95 values in children are a factor 4 higher than the median values.

An overview of **AMPA** concentration levels in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries (indicator Figure 21), sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- median values below LOD/LOQ.
- Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 1.2 between sampling sites in children.
- P95 values differ up to a factor 2.2 between sampling sites. P95 observed for AMPA are higher in children than in adults.
- In children and adults P95 are a factor 3 higher than median values.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 51

An overview of **TCPy** (indicator Figure 22, exposure biomarker of chlorpyrifos pesticide) concentration levels in urine samples of children and adults from 9 European countries and Israel, sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- Study specific differences in median values up to a factor 10.9 and 4.7 can be observed in children and adults respectively.
- P95 values differ up to a factor 4.8 and 3.3 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- P95 are a factor 1.9-8 higher than P50.

An overview of the sum of **3-PBA** (indicator Figure 23, biomarker for pyrethroids in general) in urine samples of children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 2.8 and 3.3 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- P95 values differ up to a factor 2.1 and 4.1 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- Median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values are a factor 2.5-6 higher than median values.

An overview of the sum of **cis-DCCA + trans-DCCA** (indicator Figure 25, metabolites of pyrethroids cypermethrin, cyfluthrin, permethrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 2.6 and 2.7 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- P95 values differ up to a factor 2.4 and 2.0 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- Median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values a factor 3-6 higher than median values.

An overview of **cis-DBCA** (indicator Figure 26, biomarker for deltamethrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 6 and 5.5 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- P95 values differ up to a factor 5.8 and 15 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively.
- Median values and P95 are higher in children compared to adults. P95 values a factor 2-7 higher than median values.

An overview of **CIF3CA** (indicator Figure 27, biomarker for bifenthrin, (lambda)cylhalothrin and tefluthrin) in urine samples of children and adults from 5 European countries and Israel sampled between 2014-2021 show:

- For most of the studies median values are below the LOD/LOQ.
- Median values above the LOD/LOQ differ up to a factor 1.25 between sampling sites in children.

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 52

- P95 values differ up to a factor 3.9 and 2 between sampling sites in children and adults respectively. P95 values a factor 4-7 higher than median values.

In terms of the **health impact indicator**, P95 levels of **TCPy** (Figure 28) exposure biomarker of chlorpyrifos pesticide) in children and adults from 9 European countries and Israel compared to the available health-based guidance values show:

- TCPy provisional HBM-GV are derived for children and adults (Tarazona et al. 2022).
- Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU in children exceed the provisional HBM-GV for non-cancer endpoints 10 µg/L in 2 sampling locations (CY, IL)
- In adults, P95 concentrations are all below provisional HBM-GV of 20 µg/L.
- It should be noted that these provisional HBM-GV are not fully protective because of genotoxicity (Tarazona et al. 2022).

The indicator (Figure 29) illustrates P95 levels of **3-PBA** (general marker for pyrethroids) in children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel compared to the available health based guidance values show:

- Two BE-values were derived by Aylward et al. for tiered interpretation of HBM exposure levels in risk assessment context.
- A highly conservative tier 1 screening value of 1.7 µg/L which assumes that all the pesticides that metabolise to 3-PBA have a high toxic potency and a second-tier screening value of 87 µg/L which assumes average toxic potency of the pesticide mixture, to be used when HBM data exceed the Tier 1 value (Aylward et al. 2018).
- Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU exceed the conservative tier 1 (BE-value of 1.7 µg/L) in all sampling sites in children and in 3/5 sampling sites in adults.
- All P95 values are well below the tier 2 BE-value of 87 µg/L.

P95 levels of **4-F-3-PBA** (indicator Figure 30, marker for cyfluthrin) in children and adults from 7 European countries and Israel illustrate:

- A comparison between the available health-based guidance values (BE-value 46 µg/L and HBM-GV of 80 µg/L in children and 130 µg/L in adults).
- Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU lay a factor 219 lower than the BE-value of 46 µg/L and a factor 380 lower than the HBM-GV in children and a factor 1857 lower in adults.
- The concentrations were thus clearly lower than the BE and HBM-GV values indicating that according to the current knowledge there is no risk for adverse health effects.

P95 levels of **cis-DBCA** (indicator Figure 31, marker for Deltamethrin) in children and adults from 6 European countries and Israel with respect to the available health-based guidance values (BE-value 20 µg/L and HBM-GV of 90 µg/l in children and 130 µg/L in adults) show:

- Urinary concentrations (P95) observed in HBM4EU lay a factor 3.7 lower than the BE-value of 20 µg/L and a factor 16.9 lower than the HBM-GV in children and a factor 24 lower than the HBM-GV in adults.
- The concentrations were thus lower than the BE and HBM-GV values indicating that according to the current knowledge there is no risk for adverse health effects.

A number of policy measures aiming at reducing pesticide use and managing risks to human health and the environment are already in place in the EU. Based on an understanding of current

AD5.8 – Indicators using HBM-GVs and time trends	Security: Public
WP5 – Translation of results into policy	Version: 3.0
Authors: Joana Lobo Vicente, Jurgen Buekers, Jos Bessems, Ann Colles, Liese Gilles, Antje Gerofke, Greet Schoeters, Catherine Ganzleben	Page: 53

human exposure to pesticides and health impacts, it may be relevant to **strengthen these policy ambitions to deliver a high level of protection of human health.**

In order to secure the trust of the regulated communities, stakeholders and the public, it is essential to demonstrate the effectiveness of existing policies through monitoring activities and to perform long-term monitoring of exposure levels to evaluate differences between countries and population groups, time trends, and age-related differences in exposure